

Characterisation of Chemical Constituents of *Gliricidia meculata* Leaves

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Gliricidia meculata (H.B., K.) Steud. (syn. *G. sepium*, Leguminosae), a fast growing multipurpose legume, exhibits larvicidal properties¹. The leaves of the legume contain coumarins², *o*-coumaric acid², melilotic acid², flavonoid glycosides³ and pinitol⁴. The isolation of three new along with some known chemical constituents are the subjectmatter of this communication.

Results and Discussion

Compound 1, C₂₈H₅₆O (M⁺ 408), showed the presence of carbonyl group. Its mass spectrum exhibited the presence of a uniform difference of 14 mass units and absence of [M-Me]⁺ ion suggesting a long straight-chain compound⁵. The ion peak at *m/z* 379 [M-29]⁺ suggested the existence of an aldehydic function. Its ¹H nmr spectrum displayed a three-proton triplet for terminal methyl group, a broad signal for 25 methylene groups, a two-proton multiplet for a methylene group adjacent to aldehydic group and a one-proton singlet for aldehydic proton. It formed a 2,4-DNP derivative. On the basis of these evidences the compound 1, reported first time from the plant, has been formulated as *n*-octacosan-1-al, CH₃(CH₂)₂₆CHO.

Compound 2, C₂₆H₅₆O (M⁺ 380), had a characteristic ir band for aldehydic group. The fragmentation pattern of 2 was analogous to that of compound 1. Its ¹H nmr spectrum showed the presence of one terminal methyl group, 23 methylene groups of the chain and a methylene function adjacent to the aldehydic group and for the carbonyl group. It yielded a 2,4-DNP derivative. From these data the compound has been formulated as *n*-hexacosan-1-al, CH₃(CH₂)₂₄CHO.

Compound 3, C₂₇H₅₆ (M⁺ 380), was devoid of any band in the ir functional group region. Its mass fragmentation pattern was similar to compound 1. Its ¹H nmr spectrum displayed a six-proton broad signal for two methyl groups and a 50-proton broad signal for 25 methylene groups. It resisted to the normal derivatising reagents. These data lead to characterise the compound as *n*-octacosane, CH₃(CH₂)₂₆CH₃.

Compound 4, C₃₅H₆₈O, had ir absorption bands for hydroxyl group and unsaturation. It yielded a monacetyl derivative with acetic anhydride-pyridine. Its ¹H nmr spectrum displayed signals for one terminal methyl, 34 saturated methylene groups, one methine and one terminal methylene functionalities. From these data the compound

has been formulated as pentatriacont-1,7-dien-12-ol, CH₂=CH(CH₂)₄CH=CH(CH₂)₂₃CH₃, a compound isolated from *Colocasia antiquorum*⁶. It was identified by comparison of a pure specimen of 4 from its m.p., m.m.p. and tlc data.

Compound 5, C₃₁H₆₂O, showed a negative TNM test for unsaturation and positive 2,4-DNP test and a characteristic ir absorption band for a carbonyl group. Its ¹H nmr spectrum exhibited signals for two terminal methyl groups, 26 methylene groups and two methylene groups adjacent to the carbonyl group. These chemical and spectral evidences suggest the compound to be identical with 16-hentriacontanone⁷, CH₃(CH₂)₁₄CO(CH₂)₁₄CH₃, which was comparison of its m.p.

Compound 6, C₃₆H₇₂O₂, had typical ir absorption bands for hydroxyl and carbonyl groups. Its ¹H nmr spectrum displayed signals for two terminal methyls and 31 methylene groups. On the basis of spectral data and m.p. compound 6 was characterised as 32-hydroxyhexatriacont-4-one⁸, CH₃(CH₂)₂CO(CH₂)₂₇CH(OH)(CH₂)₃CH₃.

Compound 7, C₂₅H₅₀O, had the characteristic ir bands for aldehydic group. Its ¹H nmr spectrum showed the presence of one terminal methyl group, 23 methylene groups and aldehydic proton signals. The spectral data and m.p. suggested it to be pentacosan-1-al⁷, CH₃(CH₂)₂₃CHO.

Experimental

M.p.s. were recorded on a Perfit apparatus in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded on a Jeol 60 MHz instrument using TMS as an internal standard. Tlc was run on silica gel in C₆H₆, C₆H₆-CHCl₃ (1 : 1), CHCl₃ and CHCl₃-MeOH (9 : 1) and spots were visualised by I₂ vapour, uv radiation and by spraying with ceric sulphate.

Isolation of constituents : Air-dried and powdered leaflets (3 kg) and petioles (2 kg) of *G. meculata* were extracted (Soxhlet) with ethanol (95%) separately. The concentrated dark greenish viscous extracts were chromatographed individually on silica gel columns which were eluted successively with petroleum ether, chloroform and methanol in order of increasing polarity. The progress of elution was monitored by tlc.

n-Octacosan-1-al (1) : The residue from the petroleum ether-CHCl₃ (3 : 1) eluant of the leaflets extract on crystallisation from CHCl₃-CH₃OH (1 : 1) yielded

colourless crystals (0.065 g, 0.002%), m.p. 80–82°; λ_{\max} (C_6H_{12}) 214 nm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 2 903, 1 735, 1 467, 1 375, 1 172, 729, 719 cm^{-1} ; δ 0.86 (3H, t, J 4.0 Hz, CH_3), 1.26 (50H, br s, $25 \times CH_2$), 2.16 (2H, m, CH_2-2), 8.77 (1H, m, CHO-1); m/z 408 $[M]^+$ ($C_{28}H_{56}O$) (2.9), 379 (1.6), 351 (2.4), 337 (3.0), 323 (3.4), 309 (4.1), 295 (4.4), 281 (4.8), 267 (5.2), 253 (5.5), 239 (6.0), 225 (6.5), 211 (6.6), 197 (7.7), 183 (8.7), 169 (10.9), 155 (11.3), 141 (13.0), 127 (15.4), 113 (19.4), 99 (24.9), 85 (55.3), 71 (74.1), 57 (100). Treatment of 1 with 2,4-DNP yielded orange coloured DNP derivative.

n-Hexacosan-1-al (2) : The residue from the $CHCl_3$ eluants on crystallisation from $CHCl_3-CH_3OH$ (1 : 1) afforded colourless amorphous powder (0.04 g, 0.013%), m.p. 77–79°, λ_{\max} (C_6H_{12}) 216 nm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 2 821, 2 850, 1 738, 1 508, 1 489, 1 376, 1 173, 740, 723 cm^{-1} ; δ 1.20 (46H, br s, $23 \times CH_2$), 2.20 (2H, m, CH_2-2), 8.25 (1H, br s, CHO-1); m/z 380 $[M]^+$ ($C_{26}H_{52}O$) (1.9), 351 (2.3), 337 (2.9), 323 (3.5), 309 (4.1), 295 (4.3), 281 (4.7), 267 (5.4), 253 (5.6), 239 (5.7), 225 (5.9), 211 (6.3), 197 (7.0), 183 (8.2), 169 (9.7), 155 (11.0), 141 (12.8), 127 (15.3), 113 (19.2), 99 (26.3), 85 (57.2), 71 (76.0), 57 (100). Treatment of 2 with 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine produced orange coloured 2,4-DNP derivative.

n-Octacosane (3) : Petroleum ether fractions of the petioles extract on crystallisation from $CHCl_3-CH_3OH$ (3 : 1) furnished colourless crystals (0.075 g, 0.0037%), m.p. 61–63°, λ_{\max} (C_6H_{12}) 216 nm, ν_{\max} (KBr) 2 917, 2 848, 1 460, 1 261, 1 097, 1 024, 805, 717 cm^{-1} ; δ 0.83 (6H, br m, $2 \times CH_3$), 1.20 (50H, br s, $25 \times CH_2$); m/z 380 $[M]^+$ ($C_{27}H_{56}$) (1.1), 351 (1.8), 338 (1.9), 323 (2.7), 309 (3.1), 295 (4.1), 281 (4.6), 267 (4.8), 253 (5.0), 239 (5.1), 225 (5.6), 211 (6.2), 197 (7.0), 183 (8.1), 169 (8.6), 155 (9.7), 141 (11.5), 127 (14.0), 113 (17.5), 99 (22.3), 85 (51.1), 71 (70.4), 57 (100).

Pentatriacont-1,7-dien-12-ol (4) : Petroleum ether- $CHCl_3$ (9 : 1) eluants of the petioles extract on crystallisation from $CHCl_3-CH_3OH$ (1 : 1) gave colourless crystals (0.057 g, 0.0019%), m.p. 69–70°. It did not depress the m.m.p. of 4 obtained from *Colocasia antiquorum*⁶, R_f 0.61 (C_6H_6), ν_{\max} 3 430 cm^{-1} , (OH); δ 0.86 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.23 (58H, br s, $29 \times CH_2$), 2.06 (1H, s, D_2O exchangeable, OH), 2.26 (10H, m, $CH_2 \times 5$), 4.33 (2H, m, CCH_2), 4.96 (3H, m, $3 \times CHC$).

16-Hentriacontanone (5) : Petroleum ether eluants of the petiole extract on crystallisation from $CHCl_3-CH_3OH$ (1 : 1) yielded colourless crystals (0.11 g, 0.0036%), m.p. 60–61° (lit.⁷ 59°), R_f 0.59 ($CHCl_3-CH_3OH$, 4 : 1); λ_{\max}

214 nm; ν_{\max} 2 918, 2 848, 1 720, 1 467, 1 172, 723 cm^{-1} ; δ 0.86 (3H, br s, CH_3), 0.96 (3H, br s, CH_3), 1.26 (52H, br s, $26 \times CH_2$), 2.00 (4H, br s, $2 \times CH_2CO$).

32-Hydroxyhexatriacont-4-one (6) : Fractions of the petiole extract eluted with $CHCl_3$ on crystallisation from $CHCl_3-CH_3OH$ (1 : 3) furnished colourless crystals (0.085 g, 0.0028%), m.p. 73–75° (lit.⁸ 73–76°), R_f 0.48 ($CHCl_3-CH_3OH$, 4 : 1); ν_{\max} 3 500, 1 730, 1 500, 1 486, 1 375, 1 170, 740, 730 cm^{-1} ; δ 0.89 (6H, t, J 8.0 Hz, $2 \times CH_2$), 1.20 (52H, br s, $26 \times CH_2$), 1.55 (6H, s, $3 \times CH_2$), 2.22 (4H, br s, $2 \times CH_2$), 3.96 (1H, m, CHO).

Pentacosan-1-al (7) : Fractions eluted with $CHCl_3-CH_3OH$ (49 : 1) of the petioles extract on crystallisation with $CHCl_3-CH_3OH$ (1 : 3) afforded colourless crystals (0.09 g, 0.003%), m.p. 71–73° (lit.⁷ 72–74°), R_f 0.391 ($CHCl_3-CH_3OH$, 4 : 1); ν_{\max} 2 920, 2 849, 1 730, 1 480, 1 385, 1 175, 725 cm^{-1} ; δ 0.86 (3H, br s, CH_3), 1.22 (44H, br s, $22 \times CH_2$), 2.25 (2H, m, CH_2), 8.20 (1H, br s, CHO-1).

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